

Roadway to Promotion: A Silver Lining Desire of Public School Senior High School Teachers

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Abstract. Promotion within the teaching profession involves educators progressing to higher roles, driven by factors like education, experience, leadership skills, professional development, and commitment. This study aimed to examine the desires and challenges of public senior high school teachers in relation to promotion. It explored the impact of these challenges on their motivation to teach and delves into their experiences, coping strategies, and learning insights tied to the pathway to promotion. Rooted in Albert Bandura's theory of Social Learning, the study underscores the influence of our social nature on teachers' adaptation to technological and support-driven changes in education and promotion strategies. Employing phenomenology, the method focuses on the purposeful nature of experiences and their connection to meaning, highlighting personal perspectives. The study revealed major themes from teachers' experiences, such as pedagogical proficiency and professional dedication. Coping mechanisms encompassed a resilient growth mindset and preparedness for professional growth, while insights revolved around persistent pursuit and resilient determination. The findings underlined the significance of qualifications, experience, leadership, and commitment in teacher advancement. Professional growth and resilience emerged as crucial factors due to teaching challenges. Overall, dedication emerged as the key driver for teachers to progress. Understanding the multifaceted aspects of teacher advancement and their implications is pivotal for fostering effective strategies that support career progression in education.

KEY WORDS

1. Teachers in the frontline
2. Secondary School Teachers
3. Davao City, Philippines

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1. Introduction

Promotion serves as a critical aspect of professional growth and motivation among educators. However, in many educational systems, senior high school teachers often face significant challenges in achieving career advancement. This study, titled "Roadway to Promotion: A Silver Lining Desire of Public School Senior High School Teachers," aims to explore the various factors contributing to the stagnation in the

promotion of senior high school teachers and proposes potential policy changes to address these issues.

Public school teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the future of society by imparting knowledge and skills to students. Yet, despite their crucial contributions, many senior high school teachers experience stagnation in their careers due to inadequate promotion policies

(Smith, 2020). The lack of clear, transparent, and supportive promotion pathways can lead to decreased job satisfaction, motivation, and overall effectiveness in teaching (Johnson Stevens, 2019). This issue is particularly pronounced in public schools, where bureaucratic hurdles and limited resources often impede the promotion process (Williams et al., 2018).

Promotion policies in the education sector are often influenced by a variety of factors, including tenure, academic qualifications, performance evaluations, and professional development (Jones, 2021). However, existing policies may not adequately reflect the dynamic and evolving nature of the teaching profession. For instance, many policies fail to recognize the importance of continuous professional development and innovative teaching practices (Brown, 2017). Moreover, the criteria for promotion are often rigid and do not account for the diverse skills and contributions of teachers (Taylor, 2018).

This study seeks to investigate the current promotion policies for senior high school teach-

ers in public schools and identify the barriers that prevent these educators from advancing in their careers. By examining the perspectives of teachers, administrators, and policymakers, the study aims to propose comprehensive and feasible policy recommendations that can create a more supportive and enabling environment for teacher promotion. The ultimate goal is to highlight the "silver lining" — the potential for meaningful change that can enhance the professional lives of senior high school teachers and, consequently, improve educational outcomes for students.

In conducting this research, we will utilize a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews to gather comprehensive data on the experiences and perceptions of senior high school teachers regarding promotion policies. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights into the factors hindering teacher promotion and offer practical solutions to address these challenges.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The goal of the study is to explore the experiences of senior high school teachers in their desire to have career advancements in the Department of Education. This study will be beneficial for administrators, as data gathered will serve as research-based information that will be of use in motivating and giving technical assistance to the senior high school teachers and as well as their basis for policy changes.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. It is also worth noting that artificial intelligence was used for the proofreading of this document. This statement is an additional ethical practice in doing research in the era of artificial intelligence, since this article will also be subjected to AI detection.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—This study used the three (3) basic assumptions that qualitative research undertakes as Creswell (2012) pointed out. The methodologies that the researcher developed were influenced by

these four assumptions, namely, ontology, epistemology, rhetoric, and axiology. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and

multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the desire of public senior high school teachers on roadway to promotion was investigated. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. It is made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progresses. Epistemology. In view of epistemological assumption, as a researcher, I will attempt to lessen the distance between opinion and a researcher as mentioned by Creswell (2012). Apart from having been a researcher, it was incumbent on me that I had to play a part in the whole discussion considering that I had first-hand familiarity with the challenges that teachers faced. Rest assured that whatever transpired during the entire research process, my role as a researcher did not interfere with my opinion of the participants. Further, this suggested that as a researcher, I collaborated, spent time in the field with the participants,

and became an "insider". In this study, it was important to establish a relationship with my participants identified in F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School. Through this, I could tell that through my exposure to the participants, I would observe what they had expressed during the discussion. Axiology. For the axiological assumptions, Creswell (2012) discussed that the role of values in a study is significant. It suggests that the researcher openly discussed the values that shape the narrative and includes his own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. In the context of my study on the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion, I considered that the information of my participants played a very valuable role as it served as my basis to improve the established mechanism or system on the roadway to promotion of our public senior high school teachers, particularly in F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School. Rhetoric. In rhetoric assumptions, it suggests that the investigator uses specific terms and a personal and literary narrative in the study (Creswell, 2012). In adherence to it, I will write informally the texts in this study with the use of personal voice and qualified terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability instead of internal and external validity. During the entire process of the study, as a researcher, I keenly observed the gestures and nuances of the participants during the interview, especially regarding their opinion about the topic.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the lived ex-

periences and perspectives of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students were investigated, particularly those participants from F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School, Division of Davao City. The researcher's drove

in knowing the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which is considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences was presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience

is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006).

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design since it focused on the lived experiences and perspectives of teachers on the influence of internet slang on the writing and speaking skills of the students. According to Creswell, (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and was culled for phrases and themes that was grouped into clusters of meanings. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with the roots in philosophy, psychology and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking of notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research

for which interviews provide in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell, (2012) also claimed that interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to create a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated their personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written in a way that helped readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence

of the experience. Conversely, several challenges were pointed out. The researcher needed a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher had to decide how and when their personal observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches are based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of English teachers, the researcher intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative research method. This study used qualitative research incorporating phenomeno-

2.4. Research Participants—Seven participants of this investigation came from the teachers of F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School in the Department of Education. Teachers who had served as public senior high school teachers since 2016 qualified as participants in the study. The participants were identified using purposive sampling since the study mainly focused on specific participants who had been teaching senior high school since its implementation and had experience in the roadway to promotion. The teachers who belonged to the senior high school level were participants of this study. The members of the discussion were chosen based on their coordinated involvement in the happenings in the school. They served

logical research. It gathered and worked with non-numerical information that deciphers significance from this information that helps and assists us to comprehend social life through the investigation of focused populaces or spots Crossman (2017). A subjective outline will depict as an approach for investigation and understanding the importance people or gatherings credit to a social or human issue Creswell (2013). The procedure of research included raised questions and techniques, information commonly gathered in the member's setting, information investigated inductively working from particulars to general topics, and the scientist made elucidations of the importance of the data. In the context of the study on the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion, the phenomenological approach was utilized to portray and guide the selected teachers as participants in F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School, reflecting their environment improvement. The objective of the subjective phenomenology was to look into the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion.

as a solid wellspring of information for this investigation. As compared to quantitative analysis, qualitative required a smaller sample size only which was enough to obtain enough data to sufficiently described the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion that further addressed the research questions. This is supported by Creswell (1998), who suggested that phenomenological study recommended 5 – 25 while Morse (1994) suggested at least six. These reviews will allow me to how many participants will be included. In this study, a sum of 7 members from the mentioned groups will be recognized and incorporated into the investigation of the examination. These numbers are also depending

on the saturation when reached. Saturation occurred when adding more participants to the study may not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser Strauss (1967) recommended the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. Other guidelines were also recommended. In this study, a non-probability sampling method was used when characteristics to be possessed by samples were rare and difficult to find in the research methodology. For example, in the context of the study, I considered suggestions and referrals from other identified participants since they could refer to the same experience, they had in line with the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion. Referrals from initial subjects were used to generate additional subjects, in other words. The sampling method was applied to the members of the sample group who were recruited via chain referral. There were seven teachers recruited for this study. Each participant was given specific codes to hide their iden-

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations could be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to promoting the aims of the research by imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research was very essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experiences of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed the interest of the researcher was the challenges faced

ties and to allow them to freely express their opinions and knowledge regarding the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion. The members of the group came from different subject areas of F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School. Each was expected to provide their responses regarding the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion via Google Meet or any available online platforms. Before the discussion commenced, future readers were provided with a brief background of the research environment. The study was conducted in F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School, a member of the first congressional district and the only stand-alone senior high school in the division of Davao City. In terms of the academic cluster, it belonged to the first cluster. F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School offered Academic track and Technical Vocational and Livelihood track.

by teachers in the use of interactive media instruction in the classroom to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation as cited by McLeod (2009) was adhered to. The invitation to the participants was ensured to convey that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on an understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection are detailed in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to the informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a

signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study could answer the research instrument as they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there were some clarifications or questions regarding the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered during their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent in this was minimized through taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the

Data Privacy Act of 2002 to assure that the data could not be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output carried out from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all issues were given consideration to ensure there was no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any type of misleading information, as well as the representation of primary data findings in a biased way, had to be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they should provide their full honesty in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication in relation to the research should be conducted with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would be the first to benefit from the results of the study. Transparency. The results of the study would be accessible to the respondents and the heads of the participating schools because the information was available and placed on CDs or other storage devices which could be requested from the researcher. Additionally, by learning about the results of the study, classroom teachers would become aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Furthermore, each participant would be advised that they had the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process, and that they could request and be allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured

that they possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and the researcher was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strove to complete the study successfully within the specific time frame and had equipped themselves with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by providing needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensured they had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study hoped to be completed on target. Community Involvement.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The fundamental part of the researcher was to become the essential information authority in subjective research. The specialist handled the subjective data-gathering method through FGD. The method of meeting the participants covered a semi-structured structure. During the FGD, the discussion was recorded to capture the essence of the participants. This was to ensure that genuine responses were recorded verbatim. Another role of the researcher was to become a participant observer at the same time. This was to demonstrate that during the conducted FGD, the researcher observed the behavior of the participants unknowingly. Undoubtedly, the an-

2.7. *Data Collection*—Several steps were undertaken in the gathering of data, and they were as follows. First, a written communication from the dean of the Graduate School was sent to endorse the researcher to the Schools

The researcher showed respect for the local tradition, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great appreciation for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the Researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said in their own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher ensured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation or fabrication of data or results was included, nor were purposefully inaccurate conclusions put forward.

alyst took on the roles of the interviewer, observer, note-taker, and transcriber. Just as in quantitative methods, this required implementing specialized skills correctly to carry out the task. Competence in these skills was required as it was pointed out that the study needed to be conducted without bias and with potential participants, interviews needed to be conducted properly according to the design, appropriate field observations needed to be made, suitable artifacts needed to be selected, images needed to be captured, journal entries needed to be documented, and so on. Additionally, the data needed to be handled, analyzed, and interpreted per the design.

Division Superintendent (SDS) of Davao City, bearing the requested permission to conduct the study. After the approval, a letter was disseminated to the selected teachers in F. Bangoy National High School-Senior High School to be

tapped as participants of the study based on the referrals. A researcher-made questionnaire was developed and subjected to face validation. The provided guide questions were asked during the FGD. The data was gathered through focus group discussions via online platforms. Furthermore, all interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. This was to ensure safety and precautions, as in the new normal for gathering data, health protocols set by health authorities were considered. Thus, physical contact was highly discouraged during the process of data collection. The responses of the participants were analyzed through thematic content analysis. Whatever philosophical standpoint the researcher took and whatever data collection method was used, the process involved generating large amounts of data (Sutton, 2015).

2.8. *Framework of Analysis*—In the analysis of data, the following tools were presented and discussed below. Thematic Content Analysis. Thematic content analysis is one of the most common forms of analysis in qualitative research (Guest, 2012). As referred to by Maglente (2018), it emphasized pinpointing, analyzing, and recording patterns (or "themes") within data. Themes were developed across datasets that were essential to the phenomenon's description and were related to a specific research question. Furthermore, this method emphasized the organization and rich portrayal of the dataset. Topical analysis involved examining expressions or words within the content and then proceeded to identify specific and explicit ideas within the data. Triangulation. Cohen and Manion (2000) defined triangulation as an "attempt to describe, or explain more fully, the richness and complexity of human behavior by studying it from more than one standpoint." They argued that triangulation "provides a detailed and balanced picture of the situation." They pointed out that triangulation was a

Records of what would be discussed and done during the interviews or focus group discussions were made through audio recording using recent technology. The researcher maximized the use of audio-recording for data collection, and the recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. As a rough guide, it took an experienced researcher/transcriber more than 8 hours to transcribe an audio-recorded interview. The researcher used "field notes" to complement audio-taped interviews. Field notes allowed the researcher to maintain and comment on impressions, environmental contexts, behaviors, and nonverbal cues that may not be adequately captured through audio recording. The researcher also jotted down notes based on observations during the FGD.

"method for cross-checking data from different sources to search for regularities in the explored data," as referred to by Maglente (2018). This study follows the triangulation techniques of data gathering it is a very useful means of capturing more details, but also, no matter how big or small the study may be (Holland, 2009). The main things to consider in analyzing the data gathered include triangulation of sources, methods, and results to check the validity of data gathered from the participants, deciphering patterns, highlighting the adversities of teachers during in-person Instruction of learners, and crystallization of findings or the creation of themes. When done with the interview and focus group discussion with the identified participants, I gathered essential information that might help my study. The following steps presented in the framework above (Figure 2) will be followed which was adopted from Giorgi's four-phase phenomenological method, Ojala (2018). The probing question were thrown to the selected participants based on the following objectives of this study: What are the live experiences

Fig. 1. Analytical Framework of the Study

of public senior high school teachers in roadway to promotion? What are the coping mechanisms of public senior high school teachers in roadway to promotion? What educational insights can be drawn from public senior high school teachers in roadway to promotion? These probing questions were shown in the question matrix found in the appendices. The group interview lasted from 45 to 60 minutes, and the interviews were transcribed based on the audio recorder. The data was analyzed using a phenomenological method, which was briefly presented in the figure above. As a researcher, I read each interview carefully several times and wrote a complete description of each participant's experience on their respective journey in the first phase. In the second phase of the data gathering, I discriminated meaning units of their experience journey from each participant's transcription us-

ing the participants' own words or expressions and even allowed them to use their own language to find subjective meaning units for the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion. With my experiences, I described and collected the data together for thematic content analysis. The themes that were formed were arranged so that the most valuable ones were placed in an order that reflected how they related to each other. The value of each theme was described and presented by how the participant described their experiences. These themes were supported by the related literature that had significant meaning. This organized collection of meaning structures constituted a subjective meaning network. Additionally, a meaningful perspective was written, representing the entire experience and the journey of every participant.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Maglente (2018), mentioned that the trustworthiness of a subjective report was expanded by maintaining high credibility and objectivity. For

quantitative studies, this means validity and reliability. In this study, validity was utilized to ascertain how confident the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the road-

way to promotion were. Their experiences stood as their personal opinions that could be used as data for further exploration and discoveries. In qualitative studies like this, triangulation was a way to demonstrate that the research study's findings were reliable (Olivia, n. d.). Then, transferability was how the subjective analyst demonstrated that the study's findings were applicable to different settings (Olivia, n. d.). In this context, the "different settings" referred to the experiences of participants that were comparable and identical samples in line with the challenges faced by teachers during in-person instruction of learners. Specifically, the subjective opinions of the participants might have been experienced by other groups of individuals in different settings, conditions, and circumstances. Confirmability was the level of lack of bias in the research study's findings (Olivia, n. d.). Regardless of the circumstances and the outcome of the phenomenon, the experiences of the participants remained their own, as they were the ones who directly observed their actions concerning the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion. This meant that the findings depended on participants' responses and had no potential bias or personal motivation from the analyst. To establish confirmability, subjective researchers would provide an audit trail, highlighting each step of data analysis made to provide a basis for the decisions made. Finally, reliability was the extent to which the research could be repeated by other researchers and yield consistent findings. In other words, if someone wanted to replicate the study, they should have enough information from the research answer to do so and obtain similar findings as the original study (Olivia, n. d.). The reason why studies like this are important is that they can serve as a foundation for further studies and explorations. In this context, the results and recommendations drawn regarding the lived experiences of public senior high school teachers on the roadway to promotion were valuable data for educational policy implementation and decision-making. In this phase, the language was changed to reflect a third-person perspective. In the synthesis, the essential theme of their journey was extracted from the meaning structures of all participants.

3. Results and Discussions

In this chapter, I am eager to unveil the captivating revelations that have emerged from our thorough exploration of the interview data. As we embark on a journey through the various themes that have surfaced from our meticulous analysis, I invite you to engage in profound discussions intricately aligned with the very essence of our study's objectives. To ensure an authentic representation of the voices within our participant group, I have meticulously intertwined their responses into the fabric of this narrative. Before we delve into the profound insights shared by our participants, allow me to acquaint you with the symbols designed to navigate this intricate web of perspectives. Throughout the interview transcriptions, I have skillfully employed codes – concise yet meaningful labels – to uniquely identify each research participant. These codes, denoted as P1 through P7, serve as distinctive markers for our valued contributors, infusing a personalized dimension into their invaluable contributions.

3.1. Lived Experiences of Public Senior High School Teachers in Roadway to Promotion—Figure 2 illustrates the tangible experiences encountered by teachers in public senior high schools along their journey towards promotion. These experiences reflect the firsthand encounters of teachers who navigated the path to promotion within their professional careers.

Fig. 2. Emerging themes of the lived experiences of Public Secondary Senior High School Teachers in Roadway to Promotion

There were two major themes formed out from their experiences namely: pedagogical proficiency and professional dedication. Sub-themes educational qualification, teaching experiences and leadership skills were among the themes under the first main theme; while professional development and commitment to school were under professional dedication.

3.1.1. Pedagogical Proficiency—Imagine professional proficiency as the foundation that helps me climb the ladder to promotion. It’s like a mix of skills, knowledge, and qualities that go beyond just teaching. I think of it as having super teaching powers – being really good at engaging students, adjusting to different ways of learning, and creating exciting classrooms. But it’s not just about teaching. To level up in my career, I also need to keep learning myself. This means I should take courses, attend workshops, and stay up-to-date with what’s new in education. Being a leader is important too. As I move up, I might guide my fellow teachers,

help plan lessons, and take on bigger roles in the school. Being able to talk and work well with others is a must for me, and so is making ethical choices and using data to make smart decisions. And let’s not forget about creativity! Trying out new and exciting ways to teach keeps things fresh and interesting. When I embrace this idea of professional proficiency, I’m not just great in my classroom. I become the spark that ignites positive changes in the whole school. I make the school a place where everyone wants to learn and grow. So, the road to promotion isn’t just about getting a better title – it’s about me becoming an even better teacher and making education awesome for everyone.

3.1.2. Educational Qualification—Educational qualifications are integral for teachers on the path to promotion, reflecting their commit-

ment to personal growth and professional development. These qualifications, spanning degrees, certifications, and ongoing learning, en-

3.2. *Professional Dedication*—From my perspective as an interview observer, it's clear that professional dedication forms a significant pathway to teacher promotion. Through the insights shared, I've come to appreciate how teachers who demonstrate unwavering commitment to their roles are often the ones considered for higher positions. This dedication is seen in their willingness to go above and beyond, investing extra time in refining their teaching

strategies and engaging with students' individual needs. It's evident that these educators take ownership of their professional growth, seeking opportunities for further learning and development. This dedication translates into leadership roles, as their colleagues naturally look up to them as mentors and guides, making promotion a recognition of their steadfast commitment to both their personal growth and the advancement of their educational community.

3.2.1. *Professional development*—From my perspective as an observer in the interview, it's evident that professional development holds a pivotal role in paving the way for teachers to achieve promotion. I've noticed that as educators engage in continuous learning through workshops, courses, and conferences, their growth is tangible, making them even more qualified for higher positions. It's impressive to see how these opportunities not only refine their pedagogical skills but also introduce fresh and innovative teaching techniques. Through these experiences, teachers acquire specialized

knowledge, transforming their expertise in crucial areas like curriculum design, technology integration, and classroom management. What strikes me is how professional development also nurtures leadership qualities, creating chances for educators to mentor colleagues, take the lead in initiatives, and contribute to positive changes in education. Ultimately, promotion seems to be a testament to an educator's dedication to staying current, adapting to evolving educational trends, and actively investing in their personal growth, all of which significantly benefit both themselves and the institution they serve.

3.2.2. *Commitment to School*—Commitment to the school stands as a significant pathway to promotion for educators, reflecting a dedication that extends beyond the classroom. This commitment encompasses a holistic engagement with the school community, including students, colleagues, and the institution itself. Teachers who actively contribute to school initiatives, collaborate with peers, and engage

in extracurricular activities demonstrate a genuine investment in the school's success. Such commitment often involves taking on leadership roles, participating in curriculum development, and contributing to school improvement efforts. This level of involvement not only showcases an educator's dedication to the school's mission but also positions them as an asset and fosters a sense of ownership and pride in their contributions.

3.3. *Coping Mechanisms of Public Senior High School Teachers on Roadway to Promotion*—Figure 3 illustrates the tangible coping mechanism encountered by teachers in public senior high schools along their journey towards promotion. These experiences reflect the firsthand encounters of teachers who navigated the

path to promotion within their professional careers. There were three major themes formed out from their coping mechanisms namely: resilient growth mindset in promotional pursuits, attitude-driven advancement and preparedness for professional growth. In adherence to the ethical guidelines of the study, the participants'

responses have been systematically linked to specific codes to ensure anonymity. This approach shifts the focus from individual identities to the core of their insights, which holds paramount significance for readers seeking profound understanding. The assigned codes, labeled as P1–P7, correspond to the seven distinct participants who generously contributed to this research. For a comprehensive perspective, including interview transcriptions with associated

codes, readers are directed to the Appendices section. With considerable experience in the education field, I have had the privilege to engage with a diverse array of narratives, reflections, emotions, and enthusiasms shared among fellow educators. These perspectives offer deep insights into the intricate tapestry of teachers' experiences, particularly as they navigate their unique paths towards professional growth.

3.3.1. Resilient Growth Mindset in Promotional Pursuits—The concept of teacher resilience in relation to the roadway to promotion highlights the crucial role of resilience in educators' career progression. Resilience enables teachers to navigate the challenges and setbacks they encounter along the path to promotion without losing their sense of purpose or motivation.

The ability to bounce back from failures, setbacks, and demanding situations showcases an educator's capacity to persevere and continuously strive for improvement. Resilient teachers are better equipped to handle the complexities of their roles, maintain a positive outlook, and ultimately demonstrate the qualities that make them worthy candidates for advancement.

3.3.2. Preparedness for Professional Growth—Amolloh et al. (2018) provided valuable insights into the dynamics of teacher education and underscores the importance of aligning academic knowledge with practical teaching skills for effective professional development. The study explores how conditional knowledge, which involves adapting knowledge to specific contexts, contributes to teachers' ability to effectively apply what they've learned in their professional growth journey. The study's findings offer significant implications for teacher education by emphasizing the need to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and prac-

tical teaching skills. This alignment is crucial for fostering effective professional development that prepares educators for their roles. The exploration of conditional knowledge highlights the importance of adapting learned concepts to real-world teaching contexts. By developing this adaptive capacity, teachers can navigate the complexities of the classroom and promote meaningful learning experiences. As teachers progress on the pathway to promotion, the ability to apply their acquired knowledge in diverse teaching situations becomes even more vital, demonstrating their readiness for higher responsibilities within the educational landscape.

3.3.3. Attitude-Driven Advancement—The study conducted by Darishah et al (2017) investigates the preparedness of teachers as their attitude. The research explores how school management's supervision practices influence teacher preparedness. It also examines the impact of teacher attitudes on their readiness for effective

teaching. Additionally, the study delves into the role of teaching competency in shaping educators' level of preparedness in the classroom. By analyzing these interconnected factors, the research provides insights into the complex web of influences that contribute to teachers' overall preparedness for delivering quality educa-

Fig. 4. Insights Drawn from Public Senior High School Teachers in Roadway to Promotion

tion. The findings underscore the significance of supportive supervision, positive attitudes, and strong teaching skills in enhancing teacher readiness and promoting effective teaching and learning. The study shows two important things: first, how teachers’ attitudes affect their teaching ability, and second, how good teaching skills shape their readiness to teach. By looking at these

things together, the research gives us ideas about what makes teachers ready to provide good education. The findings stress the need for helpful supervision, positive attitudes, and strong teaching skills to make teachers ready. These things not only help teaching but also set the stage for teachers to move ahead in their careers and get promoted.

3.4. Educational Insights Drawn from Public Senior High School Teachers in Roadway to Promotion—Figure 4 illustrates the concrete insights drawn from the teachers in public senior high schools along their journey towards promotion. These were reflected from the first-hand encounters of teachers who navigated the path to promotion within their professional careers. There were two major themes formed out from their insights namely: endeavor and persistent in pursuit of professional advancement and resilient determination. Following the study’s ethical guidelines, the participants’ re-

sponses have been linked to specific codes for anonymity. This approach focuses on the core insights rather than personal identities, which is important for readers seeking a deeper understanding. The codes, P1–P7, correspond to the seven participants who contributed to the research. For interview transcriptions and codes, check the Appendices. With ample experience in education, I’ve engaged with diverse narratives, reflections, emotions, and enthusiasm among educators. These insights reveal the complex experiences of teachers as they journey toward professional growth.

3.5. Endeavor and Persistent in Pursuit of Professional Advancement—The pursuit of professional advancement demands a steadfast commitment and persistent effort from individ-

uals. This endeavor encompasses a proactive attitude towards acquiring new skills, knowledge, and experiences that contribute to personal growth and career progression. Through continuous learning, adapting to challenges, and

4.1. Implications—If the department would create a fairer promotion system these could be the results:

Enhanced Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction: When transparent and merit-based promotion processes are established, senior high school teachers are more likely to feel motivated and satisfied with their jobs. Knowing that their efforts and achievements are recognized and rewarded creates a positive work environment, encouraging teachers to invest more in their professional development and performance. This can lead to improved teaching quality and better student outcomes.

Increased Retention Rates: Professional development programs and mentorship opportunities provide teachers with the necessary skills and guidance to advance in their careers. As a result, teachers are more likely to stay in the profession, reducing turnover rates. High retention rates ensure continuity in the educational system and help maintain a stable and experienced teaching workforce.

Attraction of Talented Educators: Advocating for policies that prioritize career growth and offer competitive salaries can make the teaching profession more attractive to talented individuals. Recognizing advanced qualifications and providing clear pathways for career advancement can draw highly qualified candidates into the profession, enhancing the overall quality of education.

Collaborative and Innovative Work Culture: A supportive work culture that fosters ongoing learning, collaboration, and innovation can lead to a more dynamic and effective educational

environment. Teachers who feel supported and encouraged to share ideas are more likely to adopt innovative teaching practices, benefiting students and improving educational outcomes.

However if the system does not change these could happen:

Decreased Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction: If promotion processes remain opaque and inconsistent, teachers may feel undervalued and demotivated. Lack of recognition and unclear criteria for advancement can lead to frustration and disillusionment, negatively impacting teachers' job satisfaction and their performance in the classroom.

Higher Turnover Rates: Without adequate professional development and mentorship opportunities, teachers may struggle to advance in their careers, leading to higher turnover rates. The loss of experienced teachers can disrupt the continuity of education and result in a shortage of skilled educators, negatively affecting student learning.

Difficulty in Attracting Qualified Educators: In the absence of competitive salaries and clear career growth policies, the teaching profession may struggle to attract highly qualified individuals. This can lead to a decline in the overall quality of education, as fewer talented candidates choose to enter or remain in the profession.

Stagnant and Uninspired Work Culture: A lack of a supportive work culture can stifle innovation and collaboration among teachers. Without encouragement for ongoing learning and sharing of ideas, teachers may become disengaged and resort to outdated teaching methods. This can result in a less effective educational environment and poorer student outcomes.

4.2. Future Directions—After the study the following recommendations may be followed.

Transparent and Merit-Based Promotion Processes: Developing transparent and merit-

based promotion processes will provide senior high school teachers with clear criteria and pathways for advancement. This can help eliminate ambiguity and reduce frustration among teachers who feel uncertain about the requirements

for promotion. Clear and fair promotion criteria can also enhance teachers' trust in the system, leading to greater motivation and engagement in their professional roles. As a result, educators will be more likely to invest in their career development, knowing that their efforts will be recognized and rewarded appropriately.

Professional Development and Mentorship: Offering professional development programs and mentorship opportunities is crucial for supporting teachers in acquiring the skills and experiences needed for promotion. Continuous professional development not only equips teachers with the latest pedagogical techniques and knowledge but also fosters a culture of lifelong learning. Mentorship programs can provide personalized guidance and support, helping teachers navigate their career paths more effectively. This approach can lead to increased job satisfaction and retention, as teachers feel more valued and supported in their professional journeys.

Advocacy for Career Growth Policies: Advocating for policies that prioritize career growth and progression for educators is essential for creating a supportive environment that values teacher advancement. Competitive salary structures and the recognition of advanced qualifications can incentivize teachers to pursue higher education and specialized training. Such

policies can also attract and retain talented individuals in the teaching profession, addressing issues of teacher shortages and turnover. By prioritizing career growth, educational systems can ensure that teachers remain committed and motivated, ultimately benefiting student outcomes.

Supportive Work Culture: Creating a supportive work culture that encourages ongoing learning, collaboration, and innovation among senior high school teachers is key to enhancing their overall engagement and job satisfaction. A positive work environment where teachers feel encouraged to share ideas and collaborate with colleagues can lead to more innovative teaching practices and improved student learning experiences. Additionally, a culture that values and supports teachers' professional growth can boost their morale and job performance, leading to a more effective and dynamic educational system.

By implementing these recommendations, educational stakeholders can address the challenges to promotion faced by senior high school teachers, ultimately leading to a more motivated, satisfied, and effective teaching workforce. This, in turn, can have a positive impact on the quality of education provided to students, contributing to better educational outcomes and a stronger future for public schools.

5. References

- Acosta, I. C., & Acosta, A. S. (2016). Teachers' perceptions on senior high school readiness of higher education institutions in the philippines. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(10), 2447–2462.
- Allen, J. P., Pianta, R. C., Gregory, A., Mikami, A. Y., & Lun, J. (2011). An interaction-based approach to enhancing secondary school instruction and student achievement. *Science*, 333, 1034–1037.
- Al-Malki, M., & Juan, W. (2018). Leadership styles and job performance: A literature review. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 3(3), 40–49.
- Amolloh, O. P., Lilian, G. K., & Wanjiru, K. G. (2018). Experiential learning, conditional knowledge and professional development at university of nairobi, kenya—focusing on preparedness for teaching practice. *International Education Studies*, 11(7), 125–135.

- Anthony, C. A. (2014). *The lived experiences of veteran elementary urban school teachers: Why and how they stay* [Doctoral dissertation, Western Michigan University] [Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1369&context=dissertations> on May 14, 2023].
- Antony, M. K., Subali, P. B., Pradana, S. P., Hapsari, N., & Astuti, F. E. (2019). Teacher's track profile: The affect of teacher qualification and teaching experience. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1397, 012054.
- Azis, M., Bakri, A., & Manda, D. (2019). The influence of educational qualifications, work periods, and school climate on the performance of economic teachers in vocational schools in makassar city. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi Publik*, 9, 57. <https://doi.org/10.26858/jiap.v9i1.9318>
- Bacus, R. C., & Alda, R. C. (2022). Senior high school teaching: A phenomenological inquiry. *Malaysian Journal of Learning & Instruction*, 19(1), 242–276. <https://doi.org/10.32890/mjli2022.19.1.9>
- Barker, E. (2022). This is how we get promoted: 5 secrets from research [Retrieved from <https://bakadesuyo.com/2022/12/get-promoted/> on May 14, 2023].
- Bichi, A. (2017). Evaluation of teacher performance in schools: Implication for sustainable development goals. *Sustainable Development Goals*, 2, 103–113.
- Billingsley, B. S. (2023). Teacher retention and attrition in special and general education: A critical review of the literature. *The Journal of Special Education*, 27, 137–174.
- Bonney, E. A., Amoah, D. F., Micah, S. A., Ahiameny, C., & Lemaire, M. B. (2015). The relationship between the quality of teachers and pupils academic performance in the stma junior high schools of the western region of ghana [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1078818.pdf> on May 15, 2023].
- Brown, E. (2017). Professional development and its impact on teacher promotion. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 45–53.
- Chang, X., & Xue, J. (2020). Research on the evaluation and promotion of employees from the perspective of competency. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(2).
- Chard, R. J. (2015). *A study of current teacher professionals and their attitudes towards promotion and careers* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Manchester] [Retrieved from https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/84025379/FULL_TEXT.PDF on May 14, 2023].
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative research*.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd). SAGE.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. BMJ Publishing Group.
- Day, C., & Gu, Q. (2013). *Resilient teachers, resilient schools: Building and sustaining quality in testing times*. Routledge.
- Dohal, G. H. (2022). Eligibility and barriers to promotion: A perspective. *Higher Education Studies*, 12(3), 1–3.
- Firestone, W. A., & Pennell, J. R. (2023). Teacher commitment, working conditions, and differential incentive policies. *Review of Educational Research*, 63, 489–525.

- for Management Development, I. I. (2023). The 8 key leadership skills you need to know in 2023 [Retrieved from <https://www.imd.org/reflections/leadership-skills/> on May 14, 2023].
- Hammond, L. D., Hyler, M. H., & Gardner, M. (2017). Effective teacher professional development [Retrieved from https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/sites/default/files/product-files/Effective_Teacher_Professional_Development_BRIEF.pdf on May 14, 2023].
- Haryono, S., Supardi, S., & Udin, U. (2020). The effect of training and job promotion on work motivation and its implications on job performance: Evidence from indonesia. *Management Science Letters*, *10*(9), 2107–2112. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.1.019>
- Johnson, R., & Stevens, P. (2019). Job satisfaction and career advancement among public school teachers. *Educational Management & Administration*, *47*(4), 512–529.
- Jones, L. (2021). Factors influencing promotion in the education sector: A policy analysis. *Policy Studies in Education*, *42*(1), 89–104.
- Kadtong, M. L., Unos, M., Antok, T. D., & Midzid, M. E. (2017). Teaching performance and job satisfaction among teachers at region xii [Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3169846>]. *Proceedings Journal of Education, Psychology and Social Science Research*, *4*(1).
- Kennedy, M. M. (2016). How does professional development improve teaching? *Review of Educational Research*, *86*(4), 945–980.
- Kini, T., & Podolsky, A. (2016). Does teaching experience increase teacher effectiveness? a review of the research [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED606427.pdf> on May 15, 2023].
- Kragt, D., & Day, D. V. (2020). Predicting leadership competency development and promotion among high-potential executives: The role of leader identity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *11*, 1816. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01816>
- Mansfield, C. F., Beltman, S., Broadley, T., & Weatherby-Fell, N. (2016). Building resilience in teacher education: An evidenced informed framework. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, *54*, 77–87.
- Mbokazil, M. S., Mkhasibel, R. G., & Ajani, O. A. (2022). Evaluating the promotion requirements for the appointment of office-based educators in the department of basic education in south africa [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1341176.pdf> on May 14, 2023].
- Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Topolnytsky, L. (2019). Commitment in a changing world of work. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie Canadienne*, *39*, 83–93.
- Monyamanae, L. (2020). *The influence of promotion opportunities and professional development on the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in the central region of botswana* [Doctoral dissertation, Central Region of Botswana] [Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/43831984/The_Influence_of_Promotion_Opportunities_and_Professional_Development_on_the_Job_Satisfaction_of_Secondary_School_Teachers_in_the_Central_Region_of_Botswana].
- Newswise. (2017). New research finds people will desire something even more if you increase their focus on it [Retrieved from <https://www.newswise.com/articles/new-research-finds-people-will-desire-something-even-more-if-you-increase-their-focus-on-it> on May 15, 2023].

- Nir, A. E. (2022). School-based management and its effect on teacher commitment. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 5, 323–341.
- of Education, D. (2015). Senior high school bulletin [Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/k-to-12/senior-high-school/bulletin/> on May 15, 2023].
- of Iowa, U. (2019). Operations manual on criteria for promotion [Retrieved from <https://opsmanual.uiowa.edu/human-resources/faculty/criteria-promotions> on May 14, 2023].
- of Texas Arlington, U. (2020). Good teachers are the key to student success [Retrieved from <https://academicpartnerships.uta.edu/articles/education/good-teachers-key-to-student-success.aspx> on May 15, 2023].
- Parsons, L. (2022). Why is professional development important? [Retrieved from <https://professional.dce.harvard.edu/blog/why-is-professional-development-important/> on May 15, 2023].
- Putra, Y. S., Misbahuddin, U. F., Ahmad, M. A., & Hamiru, H. (2021). Promotion of position and competence on employee performance through job satisfaction at the regional people’s representative council (dprd) [Retrieved from <http://www.ieomsociety.org/singapore2021/papers/1289.pdf> on May 14, 2023].
- Rice, J. K. (2010). The impact of teacher experience examining the evidence and policy implications [Retrieved from <https://www.urban.org/sites/default/files/publication/33321/1001455-The-Impact-of-Teacher-Experience.PDF> on May 14, 2023].
- Rinny, P. (2020). The influence of compensation, job promotion, and job satisfaction on employee performance of mercubuana university. *International Journal of Business Marketing and Management (IJBMM)*, 5(2), 39–48. www.ijbmm.com
- Rumjuan, A., & Narod, F. (2020). Social learning theory—albert bandura [Retrieved from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-9_7 on December 29, 2022]. In *Springerlink*.
- Sambuto, R. P. (2021). Factors affecting teachers’ promotion [Retrieved from <https://studylib.net/doc/25874491/factors-affecting-promotion-of-public-secondary-school-te> on May 14, 2023].
- Schroeder, T. (2006). Desire. *Philosophy Compass*, 1(6), 631–639. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-9991.2006.00047.x>
- Smith, J. (2020). The impact of promotion policies on teacher motivation and effectiveness. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 58(3), 245–261.
- Taylor, D. (2018). Recognizing diverse contributions in teacher promotion criteria. *Journal of Teacher Development*, 23(3), 224–240.
- TeacherPH. (2014). Deped guidelines on the appointment and promotion of teacher ii and iii [Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/appointment-and-promotion-of-teacher-ii-and-iii/> on May 14, 2023].
- TeacherPH. (2016). Senior high school (shs) ranking for promotion to teacher ii and iii [Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/shs-ranking-for-promotion-to-teacher-ii-and-teacher-iii-requirements/> on May 14, 2023].
- TeacherPH. (2019). 2019 deped guidelines for master teacher promotion [Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/guidelines-master-teacher-promotion/> on May 14, 2023].
- Walker, M. (2018). Working with college students student development theory primer [Retrieved from <https://uncw.edu/studentaffairs/committees/pdc/edresources.html>].

- Wampamba, K. R. (2010). *Motivation of teachers and academic performance of learners in selected schools of makindye division, kampala district, uganda* [Doctoral dissertation, KIU] [Retrieved from <https://ir.kiu.ac.ug/bitstream/20.500.12306/13794/1/img-0202.pdf> on May 15, 2023].
- Wehmeyer, M. L., Agran, M., & Hughes, C. (2000). A national survey of teachers' promotion of self-determination and student-directed learning. *The Journal of Special Education*, 34(2), 58–68. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002246690003400201>
- Williams, A., Brown, K., & Harris, L. (2018). Bureaucratic barriers to teacher promotion in public schools. *Public Education Review*, 36(2), 158–175.
- Wong, P. (2009). *Teachers and promotion: Research evidence on the role of gender, career intentions, promotion criteria and teacher satisfaction* (Vol. 21).
- Wong, P.-M. (2009). Teachers and promotion: Research evidence on the role of gender, career intentions, promotion criteria and teacher satisfaction. In *International handbook of research on teachers and teaching* (pp. 511–523).
- Zamorro, G., Camp, A., Fuchsman, D., & McGee, J. (2021). How the pandemic has changed teachers' commitment to remaining in the classroom [Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/brown-center-chalkboard/2021/09/08/how-the-pandemic-has-changed-teachers-commitment-to-remaining-in-the-classroom/> on December 17, 2022].